

Explanatory Analysis of Habits and Associated Factors Influencing Adolescent Food Habits and Health

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Abstract

This research paper is a comprehensive study on health trends amongst the Indian adolescent population, with a particular focus on the psychological factors affecting these trends. The data sample (N=740) is unbiased and is representative of the Indian population across more than 20 states. The results of this study indicate that adolescents are likely to have an unhealthy lifestyle due to varying factors such as deteriorating snacking habits, adaptation to a sedentary lifestyle, and sleep deprivation. Further, psychological factors that exacerbate adolescents' overall health include peer pressure and stress caused by regular academic assessment. Adolescents are most vulnerable to body dysmorphic disorders, anorexia nervosa, and bulimia nervosa, caused by external factors such as social media. Obesity affects males and females differently: in females, obesity leads to increased body comparisons, while in males, it leads to decreased interaction with peers. Poor food trends emerge when adolescents move away from their homes, indicating an increase in fast-food consumption. Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) - including mental health conditions, stroke, heart disease, cancer, diabetes, and chronic lung disease - affect today's adolescents at an increasing rate, driven primarily by behaviours that often begin during childhood and adolescence.

Keywords: Adolescents, health trends, school, college, peers, food trends, sedentary lifestyle, sleep, exercise, BMI, non-communicable diseases, psychological factors

1. Introduction

Healthy eating habits have become less common as young people move through adolescence, with an increasing infrequency of breakfast and fruit consumption between the ages of 11 and 15 [1]. Further, many adolescents between 15 and 19 leave their homes for educational pursuits [3]. The replacement of traditional home-cooked meals with ready-to-eat, processed foods has increased the risk of chronic diseases in urban Indians [2]. Since the legal age for alcohol consumption is 18 in multiple Indian states, many adolescents start drinking between 18 and 22 [4]. There is, consequently, an overall pattern of decreasing trends in health.

Various factors affect food consumption. Peer groups and the "fast-food culture" contribute to poor dietary choices. Other factors such as sleep deprivation and lack of exercise caused by a sedentary lifestyle influence eating habits. Psychological factors, such as stress, depression, loneliness, and anxiety, also contribute to a decrease in overall health. This paper seeks to study these underlying factors and their correlations.

2. Subjects and Methodology

2.1 Subjects

The data used in this research paper was collected from over 20 states of India. Students from various schools, colleges, universities, and NGOs participated in the questionnaire. The targeted age group was adolescents aged 12 to 24 years. A total of 740 validated responses were obtained: 376 male (50.7%) and 364 female (49.1%). The response collection was conducted in both online and offline formats. For colleges and universities, forms were circulated on social media platforms. NGOs and schools were provided with physical forms, and responses were subsequently updated in the online database.

2.2 Research Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study was designed to analyse trends in the dataset. The study examined various parameters including height, weight, exercise frequency, sleep, medical conditions, lifestyle habits, and psychological states. The parameters collected included:

- Demographic information (age, gender, place of residence)
- Anthropometric data (self-reported height and weight)
- Dietary habit information (food frequency, meals per day, meal skipping)
- Lifestyle habit information (smoking, drinking, sleep quality, physical exercise, diseases and allergies)

2.3 Data Collection and Cleaning

Data collection commenced on 7 February 2022. Online surveys were distributed among university students, yielding 513 responses. Data was also collected by visiting schools, colleges, and NGOs using physical forms, contributing 227 additional responses. Collection continued until 17 April 2022, resulting in a final sample of 740 adolescents aged 12-24 from over 20 states of India, with the majority from Karnataka, Maharashtra, and Gujarat.

Data cleaning was performed by specifying acceptable value ranges for continuous and discrete variables such as BMI and age. Anomalous outliers were omitted to ensure analytical accuracy. Participants were informed that their responses would remain confidential and that participation was optional.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data analysis was performed using online statistical tools including DataTab and Google Sheets. Parameters were categorised and compared to identify trends using summary tables, pivot tables, linear regressions, chi-square tests, Spearman's rank correlation, bar graphs, and pie charts. Chi-square tests were conducted with a significance level of 0.05. The Spearman rank correlation coefficient was used as a non-parametric measure of rank correlation between variables. BMI calculations followed WHO percentile charts as approved by the Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP).

3. Data Analysis

3.1 BMI Trends

BMI is defined as body mass (kg) divided by the square of body height (m²). Based on IAP/WHO percentile charts, individuals in the 1st-4th percentiles were classified as underweight, 5th-84th as healthy weight, 85th-94th as overweight, and 95th-100th as obese.

In the sample obtained, 30.97% of females were underweight, 11.8% overweight, 3.83% obese, and 53.39% had a normal BMI. For males, 22.97% were underweight, 18.49% overweight, 3.64% obese, and 54.9% had a normal BMI. A significantly higher proportion of females were underweight compared to their male counterparts, potentially attributable to social media portrayals of slimmer body types as more desirable, leading to increased dietary restriction among females.

3.2 Trends in Exercise

Males were found to exercise more frequently than females on average. The mean number of exercise days for males was 3.5 (SD = 2.48) and for females was 2.41 (SD = 2.34). Regular sports practice and cardiovascular exercise were most popular among males, while yoga was most practised among females.

Dividing the population into two groups - 12-17 (school-going) and 18-24 (college-going) - showed that regular sports practice was the primary source of exercise for school-going children, while cardiovascular aerobics was most common among college students. Notably, 35% of respondents reported no regular exercise, indicating the prevalence of a sedentary lifestyle.

3.3 Consumption of Tobacco, Alcohol, and Cigarettes

Of the 219 students aged 18-24, 23% were found to consume either alcohol, cigarettes, or tobacco. A chi-square test found no statistically significant relationship between gender and substance consumption ($p = 0.299$, above the 5% significance level). Alcohol was consumed by 22% of individuals in this age group, with consumption notably increasing upon leaving home for higher education.

3.4 Trends in Menstrual Cycles

76% of females experienced menarche between ages 11-14, 13% between 15-19, and 11% between 8-11. 22% reported an abnormality or medical condition associated with their menstrual cycle, including PCOD (35%), PCOS (17%), and dysmenorrhea (24%). A chi-square test revealed a statistically significant relationship between BMI and menstrual anomalies ($\chi^2(4) = 10.53$, $p = .032$, Cramér's $V = 0.18$), with obese and overweight females more prone to PCOD.

3.5 Dietary Trends

91% of participants reported no food allergies. Among beverages consumed, milk was most popular (32%), followed by tea (26%), coffee (20%), and carbonated drinks (10%). A key finding was that 79% of adolescents reported a decline in healthy eating habits upon moving away from home, attributed to the adoption of fast-food culture. 53% of students reported consuming fast food regularly.

3.6 Snacking Tendencies

55% of students reported that taste appeal primarily drove snacking decisions. 20% snacked based on sight or smell of food, while 24% were conscious of nutritional value. 45% attributed meal-skipping to examination anxiety and packed schedules. 58% snacked when hungry, 20% when bored, and 22% when stressed.

A chi-square test revealed a significant relationship between unhealthy snacking and BMI for males ($\chi^2(30) = 46.87$, $p = 0.026$, Cramér's $V = 0.16$), but not for females ($\chi^2(24) = 29.72$, $p = .194$, Cramér's $V = 0.15$). Participants who were underweight or had normal BMI were more likely to snack when hungry.

3.7 Effects of Sleep on Food Habits

A general trend of decreasing sleep duration with increasing age was observed. The average hours slept for ages 12-14 was 8-9 hours, decreasing to 6-7 hours for ages 19-24, below the WHO recommended minimum of 7-8 hours for these age groups.

A Spearman correlation test found a low but significant negative correlation between hours of sleep and meal-skipping tendencies ($r = -0.18$, $p < .001$), indicating that poor sleep is associated with increased meal skipping.

3.8 Psychological Analytics

A chi-square test revealed that both males ($\chi^2(10) = 40.35$, $p < 0.001$, Cramér's $V = 0.25$) and females ($\chi^2(10) = 38.72$, $p < .001$, Cramér's $V = 0.25$) who reported being bullied also compared their body types with peers, indicating widespread body-shaming among Indian adolescents.

BMI was significantly correlated with peer interactions for males ($\chi^2(25) = 47.08$, $p = .005$, Cramér's $V = 0.17$) but not for females ($\chi^2(20) = 18.28$, $p = .569$, Cramér's $V = 0.12$). Obese and overweight males tended to eat alone, suggesting links to loneliness and the onset of mental health disorders. Obese and overweight females were more likely to compare their body types to peers than those with normal or underweight BMI.

4. Discussion

Dietary intake is a primary determinant of health in humans. The WHO defines health as "a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being" [1], highlighting the critical role of nutrition. Global health spending reached US\$8.5 trillion in 2019 (9.8% of global GDP), yet the burden of non-communicable diseases - including cardiovascular disease, obesity, and type 2 diabetes - continues to rise, with suboptimal dietary intake as a significant driver [3].

The findings of this study align with existing literature. Stress-related meal skipping and increased substance use among community college students were similarly reported by Nguyen et al. [12]. The association between reduced sleep and snacking observed in this study corresponds to findings from the CASPIAN-V study [13]. Menstrual irregularities including PCOS and dysmenorrhea were consistent with reported population trends [14].

Social modelling of eating behaviour [15] and the relationship between depressive stress and junk food consumption [16] were both corroborated by this study's findings. The influence of the institutional food environment on adolescent dietary choices is consistent with Rathi et al. [7]. The relationship between bullying and poor dietary habits, mediated by depression [21], was also reflected in the psychological analysis conducted here.

5. Study Limitations

This study was conducted nationally and the results cannot be generalised globally. Although data was collected from over 20 Indian states, the majority of responses were concentrated in Karnataka, Maharashtra, and Gujarat, introducing potential regional bias. Convenience sampling was employed, which is a non-probability method that may skew demographic representation.

Adolescents aged 12-15 completed surveys in school seminars, where peer influence may have affected responses. Additionally, some participants may have misunderstood survey questions, introducing measurement error. All responses are self-reported and subjective, and cannot be independently verified.

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